

ENVRI-Hub

NEXT

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Abstract	
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<p>This deliverable uses the template provided by the European Commission and aims to provide brief feedback on the relevance and contribution of the project to the policy areas listed below for research infrastructures in Europe. It includes some summary of the project, highlighting the status of the key exploitable results (KERs) and the policy implications toward: Implementation of research infrastructures, Funding of research infrastructures, International co-operation of research infrastructures, Employment and skills in research infrastructures, Greening of research infrastructures., Interaction of research infrastructures with industry, ERIC legal framework, Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation, Level of connection of your RI to EOSC, Contribution to other research areas and to broader EU priorities, Sustainability of research infrastructures.</p>	

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Interface
API	Application Programming Interface
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
EC	European Commission
ECV	Essential Climate Variable
EIH	ENVRI Innovation Hub
EML	Ecological Metadata Language
ENVRI	ENVironmental Research Infrastructures
ENVRI-ID	ENVRI-IDentifier
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
G3W	WMO Global Greenhouse Gas Watch
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GEO	Global Earth Observation
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
EPOS ICS-C	European Plate Observing System Integrated Core Services - C
IT	Information Technology
KER	Key Exploitable Result
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium

PID	Persistent Identifier
PO	Project Objective
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research Performing Organisations
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation

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1. Introduction: ENVRI-Hub NEXT Project

CALL	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01
TOPIC	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-04
PROJECT	ENVironmental Research Infrastructures delivering an open access Hub and NEXT-level interdisciplinary research framework providing services for advancing science and society
Name and email of the operational project coordinator	Patricia Ruiz (EGI Foundation) - patricia.ruiz@egi.eu

ENVRI-Hub NEXT is an EU-funded initiative that enhances the ENVRI-Hub, a platform providing open access to environmental research infrastructure (RI) data and services, and links it to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Its main goal is to strengthen and expand this infrastructure, enabling the ENVRI Science Cluster to deliver interdisciplinary, data-driven services essential for climate change research, mitigation, adaptation, and risk assessment.

The project promotes collaboration among environmental RIs and e-infrastructures, aligning with the EOSC architecture and integrating advanced Information Technology (IT) solutions. It emphasises the use of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) as a guiding framework for interoperability in the environmental sciences.

Project Objectives and Key Results

To develop the ENVRI-Hub, the project aims to address the following objectives:

PO1 – Integration for Interoperability:

Unify Europe's environmental research infrastructures across Earth system domains (Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth, Ecosystem, Biodiversity) to ensure interoperable data and services. This will unlock the full potential of RI data to support the European Green Deal and the Digital Transition, forming a sustainable, world-leading research cluster.

PO2 – Climate Feedback Research:

Empower environmental RIs to conduct joint, transparent, and reproducible research on Essential Climate Variables and global climate indicators. This will deepen understanding and prediction of Earth system feedback mechanisms related to climate change.

PO3 – Accessible Platform for Data and Services:

Develop the ENVRI-Hub into an integrated, EOSC-based online platform that simplifies the discovery, access, and use of RI data and services. It will include community competence centres and analytical tools tailored to scientific communities.

PO4 – ENVRI-Hub as EOSC Marketplace:

Position ENVRI-Hub within the EOSC as a central platform for open-science services. This will enable integration with Digital Twins (e.g., Destination Earth), climate monitoring initiatives (World Meteorological Organisation - WMO, Copernicus), and support policy-relevant environmental indicators, including those for the Paris Agreement.

2. Policy Implications and Recommendations for Research Infrastructures

ENVRI-Hub NEXT is relevant for all Environmental Research Infrastructures across the Earth system domains - Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth, Ecosystem, and Biodiversity - with key ESFRI Landmarks such as ICOS ERIC, IAGOS AISBL, EPOS ERIC, LifeWatch ERIC, ACTRIS ERIC, and Euro-Argo ERIC, as well as ESFRI projects like eLTER. These infrastructures support a wide range of multidisciplinary research activities involving thousands of scientists across leading European research centres and universities. ENVRI-Hub NEXT contributes concretely to several strategic policy areas for research infrastructures, particularly those related to climate change research, environmental sustainability, the European Green Deal, and the digital transition, by advancing data interoperability, integration with EOSC, and enabling transparent and policy-relevant climate assessments.

- **Implementation of research infrastructures.**

ENVRI-Hub NEXT has delivered key advancements that bring environmental research infrastructures closer to full operational maturity. Notably, the implementation of the ENVRI-Identifier (ENVRI-ID)—an EOSC-compatible Authentication and Authorisation Interface (AAI) solution enabling secure, federated access across RIs—has laid the groundwork for seamless user authentication and service integration also in the EOSC framework. The project has also contributed to the harmonisation of metadata and data access protocols, aligning with EOSC standards and facilitating cross-domain data interoperability. By reusing proven solutions and best practices from operational RIs such as ICOS ERIC and EPOS ERIC, ENVRI-Hub NEXT accelerates the deployment of shared services across the ENVRI community. However, persistent bottlenecks remain, including fragmented governance, uneven technical readiness among RIs, and the need for sustainable funding models.

To address these, we recommend continued EU support for cross-RI coordination, targeted investment in capacity building, and long-term funding for shared digital assets and services that underpin the EOSC integration;

- **Access to research infrastructures.**

ENVRI-Hub NEXT has significantly contributed to improving access to environmental research infrastructures by developing a unified, user-friendly access point for data and services across the ENVRI community. Through the ENVRI-Hub portal, researchers can now discover and access a wide array of interoperable datasets, tools, and services from leading RIs such as ICOS ERIC, EPOS ERIC, LifeWatch ERIC, ACTRIS ERIC, IAGOS AISBL and Euro-Argo ERIC. Tools from the Horizon Europe Project ATMO ACCESS have been reused in the analytical framework. The integration of AAI via ENVRI-ID enables diverse user communities, authenticated by EDUGAIN, GOOGLE, ORCID, and specific RIs, to ensure secure, federated access. Harmonised metadata and service descriptions enhance discoverability and usability. These developments lower technical barriers for multidisciplinary research and foster broader participation from scientific communities, including early-career researchers and institutions in less-represented regions. After

project finalisation, the planned sustained operation of ENVRI-Hub as a thematic EOSC gateway will continue to support open science and policy-relevant research.

To amplify impact, we recommend further EU investment in outreach, training, and user support services, as well as in the co-design of access mechanisms with diverse user communities to ensure inclusivity and responsiveness to evolving scientific needs;

- **Funding of research infrastructures.**

Not applicable;

- **International co-operation of research infrastructures.**

ENVRI-Hub NEXT fosters international cooperation through both strategic partnerships and technical alignment with global infrastructures. Key results established in collaboration with third countries include participation in the WMO Global Greenhouse Gas Watch (G3W) initiative and contributions to Global Earth Observation (GEO) activities, especially in the areas of climate data integration and Essential Climate Variables. The project also engages with the Research Data Alliance (RDA), where ENVRI experts contribute to global working groups on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data, provenance, and persistent identifiers. These efforts promote technical and semantic interoperability between European and international systems, ensuring the visibility and usability of environmental data beyond EU borders.

Looking forward, ENVRI-Hub NEXT is expected to facilitate continued international cooperation by maintaining shared metadata standards, federated AAI (via ENVRI-ID), and interfaces compatible with global platforms, such as the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS), Copernicus, and Destination Earth.

In addition, ENVRI-Hub NEXT serves in an advisory capacity to the iClimateAction Horizon Europe project, a WMO-led initiative that strengthens science-policy interfaces between WMO, the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), GEO, and the co-development of solutions with global experts. These efforts facilitate alignment between European infrastructures and global data ecosystems.

The anticipated long-term impact includes improved cross-border data sharing, enhanced global uptake of FAIR-aligned services, and strengthened collective capacity to address transnational challenges such as climate change, biodiversity monitoring, digitalisation, and open science. By positioning ENVRI-Hub as a globally connected platform, the project reinforces Europe's leadership in the international research infrastructure landscape.

To maximise the impact, the RI Horizon Work Program should consider dedicated calls to fund international collaborations that position the EU as a strong influencer in the global policy landscape, promoting the EC climate policies for wider impact. Activities should reinforce the role of the RIs' Earth Observation data for policy;

- **Employment and skills in research infrastructures.**

A training plan supports the ENVRI-Hub NEXT project priorities by catering for the training needs of its key actors. Three categories of actors were identified as a result of a training needs assessment: 1) **ENVRI-Hub service consumers**, i.e., ENVRI and non-ENVRI researchers and developers who are equipped with a heterogeneous level of

IT skills and goals, from data retrieval to data analysis and computation; 2) **ENVRI-Hub service providers**, including operators and developers of RIs and digital infrastructures providing data and services to the ENVRI-Hub; and, finally, 3) **ENVRI-Hub service owners**, who are leading the design of the ENVRI-Hub services and sub-components.

During the project, targeted training activities and content, such as capacity **building sessions with** supporting materials and presentations, lessons learnt from **workshops, user manuals, documentation**, and onboarding tutorials, are being delivered to support the objectives of both internal and external ENVRI-Hub users and providers. These training actions will positively impact the following capacities: eliciting and translating user needs into user stories for **functional user interfaces**; selecting cross-domain **AAI interoperability solutions** to provide seamless access to multi-source and multidisciplinary data within a consolidated framework of research workflows; converging towards **common metadata strategies and standards** to highlight the added value of FAIR practices for data discovery and integration; and, exploiting **Python libraries, Jupyter Notebooks, and services Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)** to improve the overall reproducibility of research.

Considering the diverse and wide-ranging nature of the ENVRI Community, the ENVRI-Hub NEXT training strategy adopts a **cross-project approach**, based on task forces, to capture new needs across ENVRI-Hub development phases and other ENVRI-related projects. This flexible collaboration allows for avoiding duplication, maximising efforts, and responding quickly with ad-hoc training;

- **Greening of research infrastructures.**

Not applicable;

- **Interaction of research infrastructures with industry.**

ENVRI-Hub NEXT actively supports the interaction between environmental research infrastructures and industry by enhancing the FAIRness of data and services and facilitating their accessibility through the central Hub services and, in the long run, via the EOSC. The project has contributed to the development and adoption of FAIR-aligned metadata standards, persistent identifiers, and interoperable APIs, which are essential for enabling industry stakeholders (such as environmental consultancies, technology developers, and data-driven SMEs) to discover, access, and integrate high-quality datasets into their workflows. By aligning with the EOSC implementation policies, ENVRI-Hub NEXT ensures that its digital assets are not only technically interoperable but also legally and ethically reusable, thus lowering entry barriers for industrial innovation.

In close cooperation with the Horizon Europe ENVRINNOV project, ENVRI-Hub NEXT contributes to the development of a coordinated innovation ecosystem for environmental RIs. The ENVRI Innovation Hub (EIH), hosted on the ENVRI-Hub infrastructure, is a digital platform that supports Research Infrastructures and RPOs as innovation nodes within a broader community network. It connects RIs with industry, public actors, and other stakeholders to co-create new technologies and services, and provides shared resources, including an Innovation Roadmap, toolbox, and service catalogue.

This collaboration enhances the capacity of the ENVRI community to respond to emerging societal and market needs while also contributing to the EOSC Federation in the future, which has succeeded the former EOSC Marketplace as the primary access point for EOSC services. Although the original EOSC Digital Innovation Hub (EOSC-DIH) is no longer active as a standalone initiative, its mission to foster industry engagement is being carried forward through integrated EOSC structures and new Horizon Europe projects.

To further enhance impact, we recommend continued EU support for the digitalisation and long-term sustainability of the EIH, targeted funding for industry co-creation pilots, and the promotion of ENVRI innovation assets through the EOSC Federation and other European digital infrastructures.

- **ERIC legal framework.**

Not applicable

- **Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation.**

ENVRI-Hub NEXT delivers an environmental RI-wide information system that offers a set of integrated digital services, fostering cross-domain and interdisciplinary science. The ENVRI-Hub services ultimately aim for standardised and interoperable data access and discovery interfaces, which will allow RIs to evolve in the long term towards hub-compatible data management practices at the RI level. The ENVRI-Hub, digital services, consists of a Catalogue of Services, a Knowledge Base, a Training Platform, an ENVRI-ID and a hub-compatible Virtual Research Environment (VRE). A service portfolio and service management system will ensure that services operate to expected specifications, security levels, and fulfil the needs of the broader ENVRI community.

The collaboration between e-infrastructures and RIs reinforces a robust framework for technology development, enabling RIs to concentrate on domain-specific technology challenges, such as the delivery framework of the Essential Variables. E-infrastructures support this work by bringing federation capabilities such as ENVRI-ID (which offers RI-wide AAI), cloud-compatible applications that run securely in high-availability clusters, and supporting the evolution of the ENVRI-Hub services in alignment with the emerging EOSC Federation;

Exposing the data through the ENVRI-Hub enables RIs to bring datasets to a wider audience and facilitates data usage from communities other than those originally targeted by the individual RIs, augmenting feedback loops on the suitability of the data for cross-domain science research, policy-making, and added-value services. Environmental data is inherently needed for societal good, green and economic development, and climate policies. Due to this significant impact, data sharing frameworks and information services that enable the exploitation of environmental data across RIs, EOSC, EU sectoral data spaces, and worldwide networks such as GEO are critical elements to achieve the much-needed interaction among all data sharing approaches.

- **The level of connection of your RI to EOSC.**

ENVRI-Hub NEXT has made tangible progress in aligning environmental research

infrastructures with the EOSC vision by operationalising FAIR data principles across the cluster. Notable outcomes include:

- Development of a harmonised metadata framework, grounded in widely adopted standards (e.g. Data Catalogue Vocabulary - DCAT, ISO 19115, INSPIRE-based standards such as those from the Open Geospatial Consortium - OGC, EML), which supports semantic interoperability across Earth system domains;
- Implementation of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for datasets, services, instruments, and scientific workflows to enable traceability, reproducibility, and machine-actionable citation;
- Deployment of the ENVRI-ID AAI infrastructure, offering federated and secure access to services in compliance with the EOSC authentication frameworks;
- Delivery of a FAIRness assessment and mentoring toolkit through the FAIR Implementation Profiles jointly developed by the ENVRI Community and the GO FAIR Foundation to help individual RIs measure and improve their alignment with FAIR principles, including technical and organisational aspects;
- Preparatory work for establishing an ENVRI EOSC Node as a dedicated thematic entry point to the EOSC. This Node will provide federated access to services and datasets from the ENVRI community and serve as a structured intermediary between environmental RIs and EOSC Core services.

ENVRI-Hub NEXT promotes EOSC implementation by acting as a realistic mediator between policy and practice. Instead of treating EOSC as a separate compliance layer, the project embeds EOSC-aligned services into the actual tools and workflows used by environmental researchers and data stewards. This includes:

- Mapping and harmonising metadata formats and APIs across ENVRI RIs to meet the EOSC Interoperability Framework expectations — not through theoretical models, but by adapting existing production systems (e.g. ICOS Carbon Portal, EPOS ICS-C);
- Using the ENVRI-Hub as a thematic EOSC Node, the project pilots federated service access, metadata harvesting, and AAI integration at scale — functions that EOSC requires but has not yet fully standardised in thematic domains;
- ENVRI partners contribute directly to the EOSC policy processes via the EOSC Association Task Forces and Science Cluster coordination, ensuring that EOSC policies are informed by real-world operational challenges (e.g. long-term sustainability of AAI, cross-infrastructure authentication);
- The project creates blueprints and tested workflows that can be reused by other scientific communities, reducing duplication and accelerating EOSC-wide interoperability;
- Financial support for the operation of thematic EOSC Nodes, such as the planned ENVRI Node. These Nodes are essential to making EOSC work at scale

and should not rely on voluntary or pro bono contributions from infrastructure partners;

- Integrate Science Clusters and their EOSC Nodes into the EOSC governance structure, ensuring that decisions on policies, priorities, and technical architecture reflect the needs of real user communities and domain infrastructures;
 - Streamline onboarding and compliance procedures, enabling Research Infrastructures to meet EOSC requirements without duplicating efforts or facing excessive administrative burden;
 - Maintain flexibility in EOSC implementation, allowing domain-specific interpretations of FAIR compliance that are grounded in scientific practice.
- **Contribution to other research areas and broader EU priorities.**

The harmonised access to the environmental data from ENVRI RIs **is an essential** contribution to the understanding of activities and policy actions highlighted in:

- **EU Missions:** such as Adaptation to Climate Change Mission, Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030, and the Soil Deal for Europe;
- **Horizon Europe Cluster 6:** Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environment;
- **EU Green Deal:** Climate adaptation and mitigation strategies to achieve climate neutrality, Zero Pollution Action Plan, and Biodiversity Strategy;
- **UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG):** Climate actions (SDG 13), life below water (SDG 14), life on land (SDG 15), and clean water and sanitation (SDG 6).

Cross-disciplinary access to data to understand complex ocean, land, and atmospheric interactions requires datasets such as greenhouse gas concentrations (ICOS), atmospheric aerosols (ACTRIS), ocean parameters (SeaDataNET, Euro-Argo), ecosystem functioning and land use (AnaEE, eLTER).

The harmonisation of Essential Climate Variables across the RIs is a key area of research to address key indicators of climate change consistently. An Essential Variables Task Force has been established within the project to harmonise the work horizontally across all the services of the ENVRI-Hub. This work will be further exploited through contributions to the Expert Teams established in the HE Cluster 6 project **iClimateAction**, aimed at the alignment of WMO, GCOS, and GEO to support standardised, open, accessible, usable, and interoperable global observation systems for Essential Climate Variables.

A mapping of Essential Variables offered by the RIs will be conducted, and gaps in research in European observing systems highlighted. Further exploitation of these Essential Variables will require well-defined governance and standardisation at the global level.

- **Sustainability of research infrastructures.**

To ensure sustainability, we recommend:

- Pooling technical services such as metadata curation, authentication, data brokering, and quality monitoring across Research Infrastructures increases efficiency and allows scientific staff to concentrate on research and strategic development, such as improving sampling strategies or enhancing instrumentation;
- Shifting from fragmented project funding to long-term, service-oriented models, including multi-agency or EU-level co-financing schemes that can cover core technical and support services sustainably;
- Investing in people, not just platforms. Long-term funding must support the retention of technical and data expertise across RIs, avoiding repeated losses of trained personnel between funding cycles;
- Funding ENVRI cluster projects over longer periods to support the joint development of core services and tools (e.g., training platforms, interoperability layers, FAIR assessment tools). This is more efficient and cost-effective than having each RI reinvent its solutions in parallel;
- Basing sustainability funding on usage and impact, not just size or visibility, by rewarding infrastructures that support community needs, data reuse, and capacity-building.

3. Conclusions

Why ENVRI-Hub NEXT is important in the context of Europe and European research:

ENVRI-Hub NEXT plays a strategic role in strengthening Europe's leadership in environmental science and climate research. As environmental challenges grow increasingly complex and urgent, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution, Europe needs integrated, reliable, and openly accessible scientific data to inform both policy and innovation.

- Supports the European Green Deal and climate goals: By enabling better use of environmental data, ENVRI-Hub NEXT helps researchers and policymakers assess climate risks, track greenhouse gases, and design mitigation and adaptation strategies aligned with the EU's climate commitments and the Paris Agreement;
- Strengthens data-driven science through interoperability: The project connects diverse Research Infrastructures across atmospheric, marine, terrestrial, and solid earth domains, making their data and services interoperable and thus more powerful when used together;
- Accelerates the European Open Science Cloud: ENVRI-Hub NEXT integrates environmental sciences into EOSC, ensuring that researchers can discover, access, and use environmental data and services through a unified, digital platform, in line with EU goals for open, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) science;
- Enables interdisciplinary and reproducible research: Tackling environmental and climate questions requires interdisciplinary approaches. ENVRI-Hub NEXT supports this by providing transparent, standardised access to high-quality data across multiple scientific domains;
- Lays the foundation for digital innovation: By contributing to Digital Twins of the Earth and linking with international stakeholders like Copernicus and the WMO Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Monitoring Initiative, ENVRI-Hub NEXT empowers next-generation digital tools for environmental modelling, forecasting, and decision-making;
- Fosters scientific excellence and collaboration: The project brings together Europe's leading environmental research institutions and supports thousands of researchers at universities and research centres, strengthening Europe's capacity for global scientific leadership. It has a potential relevance to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (<https://www.cbd.int/gbf>).

In short, ENVRI-Hub NEXT is a key enabler of Europe's transition to a sustainable, data-informed, and digitally integrated research and policy ecosystem in the environmental domain.

Main recommendations:

- Strengthen Interoperability Across Research Infrastructures:
 - Promote common standards and protocols for data and services across all environmental sub-domains;

- Foster closer collaboration among RIs (e.g. ICOS, EPOS, LifeWatch) to ensure that data is interoperable and can be used seamlessly in cross-domain research.
- Deepen Integration with the European Open Science Cloud :
 - Prioritise the alignment of ENVRI-Hub tools, services, and governance models with the EOSC architecture;
 - Ensure that ENVRI-Hub operates as a gateway for environmental scientists into EOSC, with intuitive interfaces, FAIR compliance, and support services.
- Support Policy-Relevant Research on Climate and Environment:
 - Focus on the production of integrated data services that inform European climate and biodiversity policy (e.g. Green Deal, Climate Law, Nature Restoration Law);
 - Promote the use of Essential Climate Variables and global climate indicators in assessing progress towards the Paris Agreement and United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.
- Advance Digital Innovation in Environmental Science:
 - Invest in capabilities that contribute to the development of Digital Twins of the Earth, the WMO GHG Monitoring Initiative, and Copernicus services;
 - Facilitate the co-design of digital tools with researchers and policymakers to ensure usability and relevance.
- Ensure Sustainability and Long-Term Impact of ENVRI-Hub:
 - Develop a governance and funding model that supports the long-term operation of ENVRI-Hub within the EOSC Federation;
 - Establish community-based competence centres and training to build capacity for using and contributing to the ENVRI-Hub.
- Promote Openness, Reusability, and Reproducibility:
 - Ensure all services and data comply with FAIR principles;
 - Encourage open access and reproducible research by providing well-documented, machine-readable datasets and tools;
- Foster Multidisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Research:
 - Enable joint research across atmospheric, marine, terrestrial, and solid earth domains;
 - Encourage collaboration with adjacent fields (e.g. health, agriculture, urban planning) for holistic approaches to environmental challenges.